

Assessment of Two-Dimensional Materials-Based Technology for Analog Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT Embedding advanced cognitive capabilities in battery-constrained edge devices requires specialized hardware with new circuit architecture and—in the medium/long term—new device technology. We evaluate the potential of recently investigated devices based on 2-D materials for the realization of analog deep neural networks (DNNs), by comparing the performance of neural networks based on the same circuit architecture using three different device technologies for transistors and analog memories. As a reference result, it is included in the comparison also an implementation on a standard 0.18 μm CMOS technology. Our architecture of choice makes use of current-mode analog vector-matrix multipliers (VMMs) based on programmable current mirrors (CMs) consisting of transistors and floating-gate non-volatile memories. We consider experimentally demonstrated transistors and memories based on a monolayer molybdenum disulfide channel and ideal devices based on heterostructures of multilayer–monolayer PtSe_2 . Following a consistent methodology for device-circuit co-design and optimization, we estimate the layout area, energy efficiency, and throughput as a function of the equivalent number of bits (ENOB), which is strictly correlated with classification accuracy. System-level tradeoffs are apparent: for a small ENOB experimental MoS_2 floating-gate devices are already very promising; in our comparison, a larger ENOB (7 bits) is only achieved with CMOS, signaling the necessity to improve linearity and electrostatics of devices with 2-D materials.

INDEX TERMS 2-D materials, analog neural networks, floating-gate memories, vector-matrix multipliers (VMMs).

I. INTRODUCTION

THE pervasive success of deep learning in artificial intelligence applications [1] is accelerating research efforts toward specialized hardware with optimized computer architecture, circuit design, and even device technology. The main effect is a shift from the general-purpose Von Neumann paradigm to specialized hardware that leverages the properties of deep neural network (DNN) algorithms [2]. Logic in-memory architectures [3] are extremely interesting from this point of view: they consist of many modularized processing elements distributed in space and operating in parallel, implementing the simultaneous operations performed by neurons. In addition, each processing element contains both the logic

and part of the memory required for the task, reducing the energy consumption and the delay associated with access to a cache or an external memory [2], [4]. In fact, the main principles of “neuromorphic” silicon circuits date back to the pioneering work at Caltech in late 1990s [5]–[7], but the new wave of interest in integrated circuits for neural networks is much stronger now that there is a potent market pull and is mainly driven by the needs of maximizing data center computing capability at constant power envelope and of bringing cognitive capability to embedded systems [8].

Vector-matrix multipliers (VMMs) are the ubiquitous logic blocks in a DNN, performing the multiplication of a vector of inputs by a matrix of trained features, that is, weights,

FIGURE 1. (a) Block diagram of a fully connected layer. (b) Simplified circuit of a single VMM node. (c) Architecture of the considered DNN.

as sketched in Fig. 1(a). The VMMs play a crucial role in establishing the performance of a full DNN system, such as the classification accuracy of the network [9], the energy efficiency, and the throughput [10]. It has been demonstrated that the inference operations with a reduced multi-bit precision can reach a comparable classification accuracy to floating-point arithmetics due to the resilience to disturb the learning algorithms [9], [11].

This opens up the possibility to perform computation in the analog domain by exploiting the device physics and circuit properties (e.g., Kirchhoff laws) [9], [10], [12], [13]. It is well known that analog processing blocks are usually affected by circuit non-idealities such as noise and nonlinearity, which limit the effective number of bits of the arithmetic operations. However, there are tradeoffs among area, throughput, energy efficiency, and computation accuracy that must be investigated and that heuristically show that area and energy efficiency can be traded for computation accuracy and throughput.

An in-memory analog VMM has been designed and realized in a commercial $0.18\ \mu\text{m}$ CMOS platform [9] by using programmable current mirrors (CMs) similar to the one in Fig. 1(b). We consider this very same circuit architecture for a comparison of different 2-D device technologies, so that we can use as reference a case for which we have a full range of experimental results.

Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) are well suited for post-silicon CMOS or for an integration with CMOS technology because: 1) they provide much higher mobility than silicon in the case of ultrathin channel layers required by aggressive scaling and 2) the weak Van der Waals interaction between stacked layers is useful for 3-D integration of transistors [14]–[16]. Some recent experimental results are very promising in view of their use in analog neural networks.

- 1) A floating gate FET (FGFET) with a monolayer MoS_2 channel has been demonstrated and used to implement reconfigurable logic in the digital domain [17].
- 2) Monolayer MoS_2 MOSFETs with planar geometry have been used to fabricate fundamental analog circuits such as a two-stage operational amplifier [18].

We also include in the comparison an ideal FET with a channel consisting of a lateral heterostructure (LH) of monolayer and multilayer PtSe_2 [19]. Such heterostructure has perfect lattice match, with a monolayer PtSe_2 that is a semiconductor

with a gap of 1.36 eV and a multilayer PtSe_2 that is a metal providing a low contact resistance. The device has been simulated in [19] without defects, with ideal contacts, and with an aggressive 12.8-nm channel length, exhibiting a very high $I_{\text{ON}}/I_{\text{OFF}}$ ratio and an almost ideal subthreshold slope (SS). We use this device as the upper limit of what it could be achievable as fabrication technology improves.

As anticipated above, we assess the potential of the use of these 2-D device technologies in analog neural networks, using as a reference the experimental results obtained with a commercial CMOS technology (single-poly UMC $0.18\ \mu\text{m}$). Let us stress here that the spirit of the comparison is not to choose among different technologies, because they do not have the same degree of maturity and cost, but rather to understand the different tradeoffs at play and the aspects of each device technology that need to improve the most.

CM-based VMMs with the MoS_2 and the PtSe_2 -based FETs have been designed and optimized according to the design approach we have proposed in [9] for a standard CMOS. The performance of the designed multipliers has then been tested at the DNN level on a purposely designed network [“Net A” depicted in Fig. 1(c)], trained with the gray-scale MNIST handwritten digit dataset [19]. All the considered device technology options have been evaluated in terms of area occupation, throughput, energy efficiency, and classification accuracy.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. In Section II, we present the basic operation of the current-mode analog VMM used in our neural network architecture. In Section III, we describe the reference analog neural network used in the evaluation. In Section IV, the main figures of merit are introduced. In Section V, we extract the compact models of MoS_2 and PtSe_2 transistors from measurements and simulations, respectively. In Section VI, we explain the design techniques used to optimize the CM-based VMM for the minimum area requirement. The comparison of the considered device technology options is reported in Section VII. Final conclusions are drawn in Section VIII.

II. BASIC OPERATION OF AN IN-MEMORY ANALOG VMM

A fully connected (FC) layer of a DNN is sketched in Fig. 1(a). Each output y_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, N$) of a layer

is obtained by applying an activation function f to the cumulative sum of the products of each generic input x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, M$) of the layer times a weight $w_{i,j}$

$$y_j = f \left(\sum_i^M x_i \times w_{i,j} \right). \quad (1)$$

The sum in (1) can be physically implemented by means of a current-mode VMM, realized with programmable CMs such as the one depicted in Fig. 1(b) [9]. In this case, the x_i 's are encoded in the currents $I_{in,i}$ and each $w_{i,j}$ is the current magnification factor of the programmable CMs. The sum is provided as the total output current $I_{out,j}$, obtained by connecting to the same node the output branches of all CMs corresponding to the same j -th output element [9]. Programmable mirrors are realized with three terminal floating-gate (FG) non-volatile memories, and the magnification factor depends on the threshold voltage difference $\Delta V_{th_{i,j}}$ between the two FG non-volatile memories of the same mirror, programmed by injecting a charge in the floating gate of the CM output device.

All transistors operate in the sub-threshold region allowing to reduce the power consumption and to achieve a range of the weights variation larger than two orders of magnitude [9], [13] considering that the weight can be expressed as

$$w_{i,j} = e^{\frac{\Delta V_{th_{i,j}}}{\eta V_T}} \quad (2)$$

where η is the subthreshold ideality factor (typically between 1 and 2) and $V_T = K_B T / q$ is the thermal voltage, in which K_B is Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature, and q is the elementary charge. We therefore have

$$I_{out,j} = \sum_i^M I_{in,i} \times e^{\frac{\Delta V_{th_{i,j}}}{\eta V_T}}. \quad (3)$$

Weights are determined in the ‘‘training’’ phase of the neural network using a so-called ‘‘training dataset,’’ consisting of labeled sample images [21]. The obtained set of weights are then used in the classification phase, also known as ‘‘inference.’’ Mismatch between devices can be mitigated during the programming phase, given that this threshold voltage variation can be fully compensated with appropriate tuning of the charge injected in the FGs. This work is mainly focused on the inference phase: the experimental demonstration of programming analog weights is provided in a few papers, either based on CMOS technology [9], [12], [13], [22] or on 2-D-materials [17], using different injection mechanisms.

III. SYSTEM-LEVEL TESTBENCH

The VMM is the most recurrent building block of DNNs, instantiated in all FC and convolutional layers. Therefore, it is reasonable to benchmark different technologies for analog neural networks by comparing the behavior of VMMs.

However, in the case of an analog VMM, the statistical distribution of weights, which depend on the architecture and the training of a particular DNN, can have a quantitative

impact on power dissipation and on the speed. For this reason, in the assessment exercise presented here, we will consider a testbench convolutional neural network, ‘‘Net-A,’’ shown in Fig. 1(c), where only the analog VMMs are simulated at the circuit level in Cadence Virtuoso, while the full network behavior (both training and inference) are simulated in MATLAB. Net-A consists of the following layers: an input layer, which receives a 28×28 pixels grayscale image from the MNIST database [19]; a convolutional layer [23] with $20 \times 9 \times 9$ filters for feature extraction from images; a pooling layer [23] with 2×2 kernels, which halves the overall number of coefficients preventing overfitting; a transform level, which rearranges the 2-D data into a 1-D vector with 2000 elements; a 100-node FC layer and an output layer, composed of ten nodes with softmax activation function for the final 10-digit classification. The rectified linear unit (ReLU) [23] is used as nonlinear activation function for both the convolutional and the FC layers.

The image dataset was used for training and inference in a 8:2 ratio. The training process was performed with a supervised mini-batch method, with each batch composed of 100 images, for a total of 60 epochs.

IV. FIGURES OF MERIT FOR NEURAL NETWORK BENCHMARKING

In this section, we introduce the key figures of merit (FOMs) used for the VMM benchmarking: effective number of bits (ENOB), number of operations, latency time, throughput, energy efficiency, and area occupation.

- 1) *ENOB*: The ENOB is a measure of the computing accuracy [9]: it depends on the signal-to-noise and distortion ratio (SINAD), according to

$$\text{ENOB} = \frac{\text{SINAD}_{\text{dB}} - 1.76}{6.02}. \quad (4)$$

The SINAD value depends on the nonlinearity, estimated through the total harmonic distortion (THD), and on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), according to

$$10^{-\frac{\text{SINAD}_{\text{dB}}}{10}} = 10^{-\frac{\text{SNR}_{\text{dB}}}{10}} + 10^{-\frac{\text{THD}_{\text{dB}}}{10}}. \quad (5)$$

In order to provide a reference value for the ENOB, one should note that we have previously proved that a VMM with an ENOB of 6-bit can guarantee a 99.7% classification accuracy of the network Net-A, trained with the MNIST database [9], [19]. The required ENOB for a given classification accuracy typically depends on the DNN architecture. For example, the well-known AlexNet [28] requires an ENOB = 7 for a classification accuracy of 92% [9].

- 2) *Number of operations*: Each multiplication and addition is considered as an elementary arithmetic operation. For an $M \times N$ VMM, which includes M multiply-and-accumulate (MAC) units and N columns, there are a total of M multiplications and $M - 1$ additions per each of the N columns, corresponding to a total number of $(2M - 1) \times N$ elementary operations.

- 3) *Latency time* (τ_{LAT}) represents the time needed by each processing unit to perform a single arithmetic operation, and it is estimated through the settling time of the output in response to an input step. Considering that all processing elements are arranged in parallel, the worst case latency time of a single multiplier corresponds to the latency time of the whole VMM implementing a layer of the network.
- 4) *Throughput*: The throughput is the ratio of the number of arithmetic operations performed in parallel to the VMM latency time and is a measure of performance of the VMM expressed in term of operations per second (OPs/s).
- 5) *Energy efficiency* (EE): It is calculated as the ratio of the number of operations to the total energy consumed by the VMM to perform a vector-matrix multiplication (i.e., the integral of the consumed power over τ_{LAT}), typically measured in tera operations per joule (TOPs/J). The energy is determined using the weights obtained from the training phase for Net-A and it is averaged over many operations, each corresponding to an input vector associated with an image of the MNIST database.
- 6) *VMM area*: In a multilayer DNN, large VMMs are the dominant elements in terms of area occupation. We have compared both gate and layout area of VMMs realized with the same $M \times N$ size.

V. DEVICES BASED ON 2-D MATERIALS FOR ANALOG DNNs

In this section, we present the considered devices and the calibrated compact models (Berkeley short-channel IGFET model-silicon-on-insulator (BSIM-SOI) [24]) used to perform VMM circuit simulations. Two MoS₂ experimental devices presented in the literature have been considered, as representative of the state of the art for MoS₂ FETs: the FG memory cell (FGFET) presented in [17] and sketched in Fig. 2(a) and (b), and the planar MoS₂ FET presented in [18] and sketched in Fig. 2(c) and (d). In addition, the PtSe₂ double-gate LH field-effect transistor (LH-FET) proposed in [19] and represented in Fig. 2(e) and (f), designed and analyzed through multi-scale simulations, has been considered to estimate the maximum achievable performance of ultra-scaled and optimized 2-D material transistors. We have compared VMM implemented by means of these devices with a VMM implementation based on a standard 0.18 μm CMOS technology, typical for the analog circuit design. In order to exploit these devices for analog neural network blocks, we have first calibrated the compact model with the available I - V characteristics by considering the physical properties of each reference device; then, device geometry optimization has been performed to adapt each device to the specific application and circuit.

Concerning 2-D-FET devices, there are no standard compact models for circuit simulations including both static and dynamic behavior. This drawback makes the design and predictive simulation of complex circuits ineffective.

FIGURE 2. Representation of the benchmarked technology platforms and the related drain currents as a function of the applied V_{GS} and V_{DS} . (a) and (b) Structure of the MoS₂-based floating-gate FET (FGFET) and the corresponding drain current (with $W = L = 1 \mu\text{m}$), respectively; (c) and (d) 3-D representation of the planar transistor with the MoS₂ channel and the I_D - V_{GS} and I_D - V_{GS} ($W = 20 \mu\text{m}$ and $L = 5 \mu\text{m}$), respectively. (e) LH-FET with a monolayer PtSe₂ channel. (f) Correspondent output and trans-characteristics for $L = 12.5 \text{ nm}$ and $W = 1 \mu\text{m}$. (g) Reference structure of a standard CMOS technology (UMC 0.18 μm). (h) I_D for an nMOS with a sizing: $W = L = 1 \mu\text{m}$. Dashed lines: device measurements (MoS₂-based devices) or device simulations (PtSe₂ transistor); solid lines: compact model simulations.

Some discrete models based on lookup table (LUTs) [25] and some semi-analytical models [26], [27] have been proposed for DC simulations but without accounting for dynamic signal

parameters (e.g., device internal capacitances) and noise models. For this reason, we have selected the BSIM-SOI [24] transistor model as a reference template to reproduce the subthreshold operation of all the device options investigated in this work. This model is physically based and can be tailored to reproduce the operation of many FETs by tuning few parameters. Although BSIM-SOI has been developed for silicon-on-insulator FETs, it includes the relevant physics to simulate the ultimate ultrathin-body devices that transistors based on 2-D materials represent. The static and dynamic simulations have been performed within reasonable limits on the geometry and by considering the same operating region as the one of the available experiments, in order to neglect effects which may compromise the model validity. Both physics-based device simulations (for the PtSe₂ LH-FET) and experimental data (for the MoS₂ device options) have been exploited to carefully calibrate the BSIM-SOI model.

A. STANDARD CMOS BENCHMARK

The assessment of novel transistors is given in relation to a mature technology. The reference VMM is realized in a standard 0.18 μm single-poly CMOS technology (UMC 0.18 μm), with a sketch of a transistor represented in Fig. 2(g). This silicon technology includes devices operating at 3.3 V nominal voltage, whose I_D - V_{GS} characteristics are shown in Fig. 2(h). The oxide thickness of 3.3 V transistors is $t_{ox} = 7$ nm, which provides an adequate retention time for a neural network operation. Standard CMOS reference circuits have been simulated by means of Cadence Virtuoso models available within the dedicated process-design-kit. The realized prototype features competitive performance in terms of both the EE and area occupation [9].

B. MoS₂ FGFET

FGFETs are FG non-volatile memories that represent promising candidates for programmable logic applications [5]. Monolayer MoS₂ FGFETs have been successfully fabricated and used for a reconfigurable logic [17]. The experimental device [17] has a bottom-gate configuration with a platinum FG isolated from a control gate (CG) by a 30-nm thick layer of HfO₂ and separated from the channel by a 7-nm-thick HfO₂ layer, as shown in Fig. 2(a). It has a channel length $L = 1$ μm . Additional details can be found in [17]. The BSIM-SOI model has been fit to experimental data: the I_D - V_{GS} transfer characteristics are shown in Fig. 2(b), for a device with $W = 1$ μm . The FGFET has been modeled as a standard MOS transistor with a capacitor in series to the gate. This device is externally accessible through the drain and source of the transistor and from the external terminal of the capacitor (i.e., the CG). The equivalent model of the intrinsic MOSFET has the same oxide thickness of the original device, that is, $t_{ox} = 7$ nm, which guarantees an acceptable retention time. Due to the missing experimental data for a complementary pMOS, a virtual pMOS device has been conceived using similar model parameters as the ones obtained for the nMOS, leading to a device with almost mirrored characteristics. Finally, the I_{off} of the FGFET and

of the virtual pMOS were aligned by tuning the threshold voltages, which can be done through a proper choice of the work function of the CG.

C. PLANAR MoS₂ TRANSISTOR

As in the single-poly CMOS option, a planar MoS₂ MOSFET can be used to realize a three-terminal FG cell by adding a capacitor in series to the gate. The experimental MoS₂ device presented in [18] and sketched in Fig. 2(c) has already been used to implement an operational amplifier (OPAMP) [18]. The device has been realized as follows: an MoS₂ film for the channel, grown by chemical vapor deposition on a silicon substrate, separated by a 30-nm-thick Al₂O₃ from the Ti/Au back-gate. The fabricated MoS₂ transistor features a large on/off current ratio of eight orders of magnitude [18], as shown in Fig. 2(d). In the same figure, the I_D - V_{GS} of the BSIM-SOI model, calibrated to reproduce experimental I - V characteristics in the subthreshold region, are shown. Also in this case, a virtual pMOS was derived from the calibrated device, by changing the channel type from “n” to “p.” After the calibration, some geometrical parameter has been modified in order to get a device suitable for the specific application. For instance, an oxide thickness of 30 nm does not allow to program or erase the floating-gate memory, thus the t_{ox} was lowered down to 10 nm. The reduced $t_{ox} = 10$ nm provides a steeper SS with respect to the original device. Finally, I_{off} was also tuned by increasing the threshold voltage.

D. PtSe₂ LH-FET

As an ideal 2-D material device, we have also considered the PtSe₂ double-gate LH-FET proposed in [19]. This is only a concept based on simulations, and no experimental data have been provided up to date.

The device is based on a channel obtained with an LH consisting of a monolayer PtSe₂ region under the gate and by a multilayer PtSe₂ for the source and drain regions, as shown in Fig. 2(e). The multilayer PtSe₂ is a metal, enabling low contact resistance, whereas the monolayer PtSe₂ is a semiconductor with an energy gap of 1.36 eV. The I - V characteristics for an LH-FET with channel length in the range of few nanometers have been simulated by considering only ballistic transport and ideal contact resistance [19]. A model with a so detailed physical description is not adequate to perform circuit simulations with several devices. Thus, also in this case, we have calibrated a BSIM-SOI model. The device is ambipolar, that is, it can be operated in both nMOS and pMOS modes based on the bias condition. However, we have realized two separate calibrations for each operation mode to independently optimize the threshold voltages: the resulting I_D - V_{GS} transfer characteristics of the nMOS for $V_{DS} = 1$ and 0.5 V are shown in Fig. 2(f) (the pMOS characteristics are symmetrical). To obtain an acceptable retention time, the silicon oxide thickness has been increased to 7 nm (the original equivalent oxide thickness of the transistor for logic was 0.5 nm), while keeping the other parameters unchanged. The increased t_{ox} of course leads to an

electrostatics degradation, resulting in very low on current of 10 nA at $V_{GS} = V_{DS} = 0.5$ V.

VI. PROGRAMMABLE CM DESIGN

The inputs of a CM-based VMM are encoded as a vector of currents with a full-scale value $I_{in,MAX}$, which is properly chosen in order to ensure the required ENOB. In addition, the selected supply voltage is the minimum V_{DD} which guarantees constant THD and SNR [9]. From the architectural prospective, there are few possible topologies for programmable CMs. Here we consider two options: the symmetric simple CM [SSCM, Fig. 3(a)] and the symmetric cascode CMs [SCCM, Fig. 3(b)]. The FG basic cell is used in both the input and output cells of the mirror, to maximize the symmetry, so that the current magnification factor only depends on the threshold voltage different of the two FG devices of the mirror. We have verified that the use of a “dummy” input FG ensures a better linearity of the multiplier in the whole input current range, compared to the case where the FG cell is employed only in the multiplying stage [9].

For any considered technology, a symmetric simple and/or cascode CM have been carefully designed with proper transistor sizing and operating current values in order to obtain a given ENOB accuracy, by relying on the design methodology reported in [9].

We assume that an $M \times N$ layer is followed by an $N \times K$ layer. In our implementation, the input current signal is provided to a diode-connected transistor, connected to N (or K , for the second VMM) columns with N (K) parallel C_{GS} parasitic capacitances.

In order to address the fan-out issue, we assume that:

- 1) the output signals are processed by an activation function (not implemented in circuit in our work), before being transferred to the next layer;
- 2) the activation function of the first layer is designed in a way to provide a magnified output current (by a factor of K) to the next VMM, realized by p-type CMs with a magnification factor of K . Then, the input-cell transistor width of the second VMM is sized K times the width of the multiplying-cell transistors; for consistency, we also assume that the M input cells of the first $M \times N$ VMM are sized accordingly (with a width sized N times the width of the multiplying-cell transistors);
- 3) for the N output currents of the first layer (and the K output currents of the second layer), they are mirrored by N (K) p-type CMs, similar to the single-cell case represented in Fig. 3. The p-type current-mirror transistors are sized with a width equal to $4 \times M$ ($4 \times N$) times the n-type ones, in order to work in a similar operating region. These outputs are sent to the activation function.

In this configuration, each multiplying cell operates at the nominal current, and the latency becomes independent of the VMM size.

Important parameters for the sizing of the CM are also C_{MULT} and C_{IN} , the capacitances between the CG and the FG of the multiplying and input FG devices of the mirror, respectively. We call “coupling ratio” the ratio C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} ,

FIGURE 3. Schematic of (a) symmetric simple CM (SSCM) and (b) symmetric cascode CM (SCCM).

where $C_{nMOS} = C_{ox} \times LW$ and C_{ox} is the FET oxide capacitance per unit area, and “capacitance ratio” the ratio C_{IN}/C_{MULT} .

The finite coupling ratio C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} introduces non-idealities due to a finite electrostatic coupling, since $\eta = (1 + C_{nMOS}/C_{MULT})$, which degrade the mirror linearity. On the other hand, a large coupling ratio would imply a large capacitance area and high area occupation. Therefore, a different optimization approach is proposed in this article: C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} and C_{IN}/C_{nMOS} have been independently optimized to compensate for the input-cell/multiplying-cell asymmetry rising from different drain bias. This approach enables quite good linearity characteristics for the designed CMs, with no need to use extremely large area for the capacitors.

Only for the MoS₂ FGFET, an FG structure is intrinsic to the cell, and therefore the coupling ratio is always smaller than 1, since the dielectric between CG and FG has to be thicker than the tunnel dielectric, and the capacitors have the same area. This is the solution that minimizes the CM area. For the standard CMOS, C_{IN} and C_{MULT} were realized with pCAPs, similar to the VMM reported in [9]. For the planar MoS₂ and PtSe₂, an ideal capacitor in series to the gate of a transistor was used to reproduce the memory cell, while the layout area was calculated by using the same rules as for the pCAP (see Supplementary Material). If a separate capacitor in series to the FET is used, the coupling ratio can also be larger than 1.

Beyond nonlinearity, also noise can degrade the ENOB of a VMM. In this regard, we have considered the default model available in the BSIM-SOI template, without calibration due to the lack of experimental data for noise in the 2-D devices. This is consistent with the assumption that with technology optimization, 2-D devices can exhibit a level of noise comparable to CMOS devices.

By considering the design of the PtSe₂ CM, first we have optimized the THD by varying both C_{IN}/C_{nMOS} and C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} ratios (with $C_{IN} = C_{MULT}$). Once the optimal C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} ratio has been found, we have fixed the nMOS size and the C_{IN}/C_{MULT} ratio has been varied to compensate for the asymmetry between the input and the multiplication. The simulated SSCM shows poor THD values, that is, lower

FIGURE 4. Linearity (THD) curves of the PtSe₂-based VMMs reported for symmetric simple (solid lines) and symmetric cascode (dashed lines) topologies (a) as a function of the coupling ratio C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} and (b) for the C_{IN}/C_{MULT} coupling ratio variation for a fixed C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} .

TABLE 1. VMM Sizing for the Maximum ENOB.

Tech	UMC 0.18 μ m		PtSe ₂ (sim)	MoS ₂		FGFET
Topology	SSCM	SCCM	SCCM	SSCM	SCCM	SSCM
Max. ENOB	7	7	6	5	5	5
W (μ m)	6	6	0.6	1	1	1
L (μ m)	1.5	1.25	0.06	2	1.5	1
C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS}	25	9	0.7	0.7	0.1	0.7
C_{IN}/C_{MULT}	1	1	0.6	0.5	1	1

than 20 dB [see Fig. 4(a)] for any C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} , and further trimming of C_{IN}/C_{MULT} ratio leads only to a slight improvement [see Fig. 4(b)]. On the other hand, the cascode topology reaches a THD of 30 dB for $C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} = 0.7$ [see Fig. 4(a)]. Therefore, only cascode mirrors can reach an ENOB of 5. A similar optimization approach can also be applied to the other devices and for a different ENOB.

A 6 bit precision is achieved for the PtSe₂ cascode option by using the following parameters: channel length of 60 nm and width of 0.6 μ m, $C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} = 0.7$, and $C_{IN}/C_{MULT} = 0.6$ (see Table 1). As regard to the PtSe₂ SSCM option, the achievable accuracy is too low to be exploited for the target application and then it will not be considered in the following.

The same optimization technique has also been applied for VMM implemented with the other considered devices. In Table 1, we summarized the sizing corresponding to the maximum reachable ENOB for each technology for both the SSCM and SCCM topologies. For instance, the VMM realized with MoS₂ transistors can reach the maximum accuracy of ENOB = 5. The UMC 0.18 μ m CMOS platform can reach an ENOB = 7, for a coupling ratio larger than 1. It should be emphasized that the FGFET devices has an incorporated FG cell with fixed width and length which cannot be tuned independent of the nMOS, thus a variation of the FGFET geometry corresponds to a variation of both the internal transistor and of the associated FG capacitor. Instead, it is possible to realize a device with a different oxide thickness between the CG and the FG in order to trim the C_{MULT}/C_{nMOS} ratio, if necessary. In this case, only an SSCM topology was designed and tested.

VII. BENCHMARK AND DISCUSSION

Minimum area VMMs were designed for different ENOB specifications through extensive parametric simulations. Extracted FOMs for the designed VMMs are then used to compare the different device/materials options. Table 2 (see Supplementary Material) summarizes the geometrical and electrical design characteristics and the corresponding FOMs, defined in Section IV. It is important to note that the area occupation was calculated with two different approaches: by considering only the gate area, or by considering a possible physical layout (details of the layout area are in the Supplementary Material).

In general, the area increases for a higher ENOB due to the longer devices required to achieve an improved linearity and to increased width needed to meet the SNR specification [9]. Only the UMC 0.18 μ m technology can reach a 7 bit specification with 7.43 and 4.05 mm² layout area for the SSCM and SCCM cases, respectively, considering a 100 \times 100 multiplier (Table 2 in Supplementary Material). The PtSe₂ CM can be sized for a 6 bit ENOB using the cascode mirrors. All the considered technologies can reach an ENOB target of 5 or 4, even though only the SSCM topology is possible for the FGFET devices, and only SCCM can operate with such a precision for the PtSe₂ devices. As we mentioned, the PtSe₂ option represents an ideal asymptotic reference case, and indeed, for a given ENOB, the PtSe₂ VMM occupies the smallest area, being more than ten times smaller than the FGFET case and more than two orders of magnitude smaller than the planar technologies (MoS₂ and standard CMOS). The CMOS VMMs are almost 50% smaller than the planar MoS₂ counterparts featuring the same ENOB, except for the 4-bit SCCM, where the CMOS has only a 23% advantage over the planar MoS₂ counterpart. Finally, due to the vertical integration of the FGFET memory, the layout areas of the FGFET implementations are much smaller than those of the other solutions with similar device size.

In Figs. 5 and 6, the EE (expressed as TOPs/J) is benchmarked against the number of operations per layout area and throughput, respectively. One should note that for the

FIGURE 5. Comparison of area and EE of the designed CM-based VMM implemented with the considered technologies for different computation accuracy. Red symbols and lines: SSCMs; blue symbols and lines: SCCM.

FIGURE 6. Comparison of throughput and EE of the designed CM-based VMM implemented with the considered technologies for different computation accuracy. Circle symbols: SSCMs; square symbols: SCCM.

same ENOB and the same device type, the SCCM topologies outperform the SSCM ones in terms of area occupation, even if they require a higher number of devices, while the SSCM case has a better EE than SCCM since it can operate at lower currents for the same linearity conditions (Table 2 in Supplementary Material).

A partially expected but still remarkable observation is that, for a given technology, an increased ENOB can be obtained at the cost of a larger area, lower EE, and throughput. System-level and application-level optimization is therefore key at the design stage of the analog VMM.

Among considered technologies, the performance of the ideal PtSe₂ platform represents an asymptotic limit in terms

of both energy consumption and throughput. For instance, if we consider the ENOB = 4 case, an EE of 7.63E3 TOPs/J can be reached with the PtSe₂ VMM. This EE value is $\times 183$, $\times 277$, and almost $\times 2084$ higher than the CMOS (41.6 TOPs/J), MoS₂ FGFETs (27.5 TOPs/J), and planar MoS₂ (3.66 TOPs/J) platforms for the same ENOB, respectively. Similarly, the simulated PtSe₂ has the lowest τ_{LAT} and outperforms other technologies in terms of throughput for the same ENOB case, which is from $\times 3$ to three decades faster than the other technologies.

Considering the two experimental MoS₂ devices, the FGFET achieves a higher EE due to a lower supply voltage and $I_{\text{in,MAX}}$. On the other hand, the standard CMOS has two orders of magnitude of lower latency than the one achieved by using fabricated MoS₂ devices, and therefore reaching a higher EE, despite an almost $\times 40$ of $I_{\text{in,MAX}}$.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have investigated the use of 2-D material devices in the design of dedicated hardware for analog deep neural networks using in-memory computing, considering the same architecture based on current-mode analog VMMs. Layout area, EE, and throughput have been extracted for different target ENOB. The ideal PtSe₂ LH-FET transistor simulated in [19] provides asymptotic performance limits with more than one order of magnitude better energy efficiency and area occupation for similar accuracy than standard CMOS. Among two experimental MoS₂ options, the FGFET [17] presents an EE comparable to the standard CMOS, despite being slower, while it is advantageous in terms of area occupation. Estimations performed on experimental MoS₂ planar MOSFETs, presented in [18], show a comparable area occupation with the standard CMOS. However, the planar MoS₂ device presents the lowest EE and throughput compared to the considered technologies. It is also important to note that only the CMOS case achieves ENOB = 7, which clearly means that is very important to improve the electrostatics of devices with 2-D materials leading to a better linearity.

As a final remark, let us stress that the scope of this comparison is limited to CM-based VMM and results can be different for other implementations, such as memristor-based ones. We also would like to highlight the fact that for MoS₂ options we have considered experimentally demonstrated devices, assuming that deep trap states—often responsible for extremely slow transients [29]—are under control. Very large improvements of the implementations based on MoS₂ FETs can be obtained if contact resistances (that are more than 10 k $\Omega/\mu\text{m}$ in the considered devices) are reduced, leading to higher currents and therefore lower latency.

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